

COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT IN SUPPORTING MIGRANT WORKERS' RESILIENCE: THE CASE OF LONTAR VILLAGE, INDONESIA

MUNARNI ASWINDO

Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia, Post Graduate Student, School of Strategic and Global Studies.
Corresponding Email: m.aswindo@gmail.com

ARTHUR JOSIAS SIMON RUNTURAMBI

Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia, Associate Professor, School of Strategic and Global Studies.

MARGARETHA HANITA

Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia, Associate Professor, School of Strategic and Global Studies

Abstract

Many facts demonstrate how vulnerable Indonesian Migrant Workers (IMW) are to various risks associated with their work, such as legal problems, domestic issues, and economic dependence, particularly for those who travel through non-procedural routes (illegally). This qualitative study aims to analyze the empowerment efforts carried out by the Indonesian Migrant Workers' Volunteer Community (Kawan PMI) in Lontar Village and their impact on migrant worker resilience. The information was gathered through a literature review, observation, and interviews, then descriptively and analytically analyzed. The results of the analysis show that the empowerment by the Kawan PMI in Lontar Village aims to prevent the non-procedural placement of IMW as well as improving the economies of the IMW. Empowerment activities have conceptually fulfilled the aspects of community empowerment, which include the aspects of enabling, empowering, and protecting. Empowerment by Kawan PMI in Lontar Village also supports IMW's resilience, both in terms of individual and social resources in facing economic, domestic, and migration risks.

Keywords: Community empowerment; Migrant Worker; Risk Factor, Protective Factor, Resilience

1. INTRODUCTION

Although it has been recognized as a basic right, the difficulty of getting a job is still a major problem that is intertwined with the increasing unemployment rate (BPS, 2020). The government's inability to provide job opportunities for the community has ultimately encouraged a number of Indonesians in their productive age to migrate to other countries. Economic difficulties (poverty) are still the main reason why people choose to work abroad as migrant workers (Sumardiani, 2014; Skeldon, 2006).

So far, Indonesia still occupies the position as the country in Asia that sends the most migrant workers (Nuraeny, 2015). In 2019, the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) recorded the number of PMI shipments reaching 276,553, with three main destination countries, namely East Asia (57%), Southeast Asia (38%), and the Middle East (3%), as well as Europe and others (2%) (Awsindo, Hanita & Simon, 2021).

A number of studies have proven that the existence of migrant workers has contributed significantly to economic development, both for the country of origin and the host country (Wang & Jing, 2012), for example, from the aspect of remittances (Azam, 2015). According to World Bank records, the contribution of remittances from Indonesian Migrant Workers (IMW) reached 8.9 billion US dollars, or equivalent to Rp. 118 trillion in 2016. (Hanifah, 2020).

Apart from the positive side, the large number of PMI abroad also leaves a negative side such as the risk of violating the law, economic risk, and the risk of household problems. Based on data from the Indonesian Global Workers Report, the number of PMIs working abroad is recorded at more than 9 million people, with 3/4 of them being low-skilled workers. Of the 9 million migrant workers, around 32% work as domestic helpers. Most of these PMIs do not know the official and safe working procedures, which ultimately results in them being trapped in the exploitation of illegal PMI placement networks (Arfa, 2016).

This IMW's vulnerability cannot be taken lightly as a PMI issue. The employment problem does not only intersect with economic problems, but is also one of the pillars for political stability, socio-culture, as well as national defense and security, especially in the future (Sunarso & Lestari, 1995).

The Protection and Empowerment of IMW is one of the main priorities of Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). One of the programs initiated by BP2MI is the Indonesian Migrant Workers' Volunteer Community (Kawan PMI). In the Regulation of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency Number 1 of 2022, it explains that PMI Friends are a group of people who have concerns, take sides, and are committed to helping facilitate access to services for the placement and protection of Indonesian migrant workers from legal, economic, and social aspects before, during, and after work established at the community level by the BP2MI.

Based on this, it is interesting to examine how the empowerment efforts carried out by Kawan PMI for the IMW community support IMW's resilience to a number of risk factors, both from the economic side and household and risks associated with working abroad.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Community Empowerment and Development

Prasodjo (2004) explains that community empowerment is a concept that emerged around the 1970s. Empowering means "increasing one's capacity" to analyze and act on the problem at hand (Kent, 1988). In line with this view, Carlzon and Macauley explain that empowerment means freeing someone from rigid control and giving them the freedom to be responsible for their ideas and thoughts, decisions, and actions (Wasistiono, 1998; Laverack, 2006).

In relation to development, community empowerment is an effort to include community participation in development by involving the community in the whole process, analytical skills, and development planning starting from the area where they work (Moeliono, et al.,

1994). The Chamber calls it an economic development based on community values in a paradigm that is people-centered, participatory, empowerment, and sustainable (Noor, 2011).

Laverack (2001) himself stated that community empowerment is the central key to the development of community welfare. Development that involves community participation will not only reduce poverty but also maximize the rate of economic growth (Craig & Mayo, 1995).

2.2 Community Empowerment Theory

According to Noor, community empowerment efforts (empowering) can be studied through three aspects: First, the Enabling aspect, namely efforts to create an atmosphere that allows community potential to develop; Second, the Empowering aspect, namely strengthening the potential of the community through concrete steps involving the provision of various inputs and opening up various opportunities that will make the community more empowered; Third, the Protecting aspect, namely protecting and defending the interests of the weak (Noor, 2011).

Furthermore, Putri (2019) explained that in an effort to optimize the goals and meaning of community empowerment, a number of basic principles are needed as guidelines for its implementation. In general, there are seven principles in order to optimize the process of strengthening and empowering communities to be independent, prosperous, and participatory, namely: 1) awareness; 2) education and training; 3) network strengthening; 4) strength development; 5) strengthening social capital; 6) strengthening capacity; and 7) recognition.

2.3 Migrant Worker Resilience

The American Psychological Association defines resilience as "the process of adapting well in the face of adversity, trauma, tragedy, threat, or even a significant source of stress (Southwick et al., 2014). This term is used to describe a process by which people not only manage efforts to overcome life's difficulties but also create and maintain a life that is meaningful and can contribute to the people around them (Hook, 2008).

Currently, the concept of resilience has been widely used in studies of migrant workers. The concept of resilience is useful in providing insight into how groups of migrant workers and their families deal with the many stresses they face. As stated by Van der Ham et al. (2014):

“The strengths perspective and resilience literatures, “obligate us to understand that however downtrodden, beaten up, sick, or disheartened and demoralized, individuals have survived, and in some cases even flourished.” This observation appears highly relevant in the context of migrant workers.”

Resilience is believed to be a factor that can minimize the negative effects of stress and encourage a person's successful adaptation to change (Rutter, 1993). This ability changes over time and is reinforced by protective factors, namely: (a) individual resources, which are characteristics of a person such as coping strategies (empathy) for the greater suffering of others; and (b) social resources, which are relationships and support networks (organizations) inside or outside the family. Furthermore, according to Saleebey (2000), the resilience-based approach is closely related to the concept of empowerment, which includes activities to help individuals, families, and communities recognize and utilize their capacities.

A number of researchers, such as Wong and Song, used the concept of resilience in their studies to examine the risks and contributing factors that affect the mental health of migrant workers in Shanghai, China (Wong & Song, 2008). In her research, Van der Ham also describes various factors that contribute to the resilience of female domestic workers from the Philippines (Van der Ham et al., 2014).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

This study analyzes community empowerment efforts in the Indonesian Migrant Workers' Volunteer Community (Kawan PMI) in London Village in relation to the resilience of Indonesian migrant workers. Empowerment efforts are analyzed through the concept of empowerment by M. Noor, which consists of three aspects, namely enabling, empowering, and protecting aspects.

Figure 2.2: Conceptual Framework

Source: Secondary Data

This research will also look at the impact of implementing empowerment on the community in the context of PMI resilience. The concept of PMI resilience refers to Saleebey's concept of protective factors, which are divided into individual resources and social resources in dealing with economic risks, household risks, and occupational risks as IMW.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses qualitative research design. According to Creswell, qualitative research methods are research that produces descriptive data as an investigative process that slowly makes sense of a social phenomenon by differentiating, comparing, duplicating, cataloging, and classifying research objects (Creswell, 2014). In addition, qualitative research is also focused on answering how a phenomenon occurs in order to find emerging patterns (Kim, Sefcik & Bradway, 2017).

Qualitative research was conducted in order to explain the empowerment efforts provided by Kawan PMI Lontar Village, as well as their impact on the migrant worker community and their resilience in facing various risks. The research will take place in Lontar Village, Indonesia. This location was chosen because the majority of Londoners prefer to work abroad. In addition, it is known that there is an active role of local communities in the Indonesian Migrant Workers' Volunteer Community (Kawan PMI), which was initiated and fostered by the Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI).

Data collection techniques in this study include literature study, observation and interviews. In this study, data validation was also carried out through triangulation using various informants such as migrant workers, activists, empowerment assistants, government agencies and academics. The results of the research are presented in a descriptive-analytical description in the form of a narrative that describes the object of research as a whole.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Demographic Condition of Migrant Workers in Lontar Village

The interesting thing about Lontar Village is the fact that, apart from being fishermen and seaweed farmers, many villagers also work as migrant workers. In fact, the number reaches around 15% of the total working population of Lontar Village. Migrant workers themselves are the third largest type of work after fishermen and seaweed farmers.

Table 4.1: Lontar Villagers' Type of Occupation

Type of Work	Sum
Fisherman	1.327
Fisherman's worker	852
Seaweed Farmer	1.021
Employee	50
Entrepreneur/trader	80
Army/Police	7
Migrant Workers	1029
Farm workers	20
carpentry	25
Taxibike	54
Teacher	64
Student	2201
Etc	28
Unemployment	234

Source: Lontar Village Profile, 2019 (edited)

According to information from the Serang BP2MI Agency, an average of two to three Lontar Village residents go abroad to become PMI every day. The high interest of rural communities in working abroad can be understood if you look at the current social conditions of rural

communities. The problem of poverty itself is still a problem faced by most of the residents of Lontar Village.

Ambar (2004) argues that the indicator of poverty is if a person is in a completely limited condition in meeting their basic needs. In the context of Lontar Village, for example, the condition and level of poverty can be seen from data from the Central Bureau of Statistics of Serang Regency, which recorded that there were 369 families who were still classified as pre-prosperous families (pre-KS). The Pre-Ks stage itself is a family that does not meet one of the 6 (six) indicators of "basic family needs," such as clothing and housing (BPS, 2021).

Although most of the people of Lontar Village work as fishermen and have a side business as seaweed farmers, the structure of fishermen's lives is in fact not free from the problem of poverty. As explained by Mubyarto (1984), when compared to other community groups, for example in the agricultural sector, fishermen can be said to be the least prosperous social group. The poverty experienced by fishermen is reflected in, among other things, the average monthly income of only around IDR 250,000 to IDR 400,000 per month (Imron, 2003).

From the results of interviews with a number of residents of Lontar Village, it is found that the causes of poverty among Lontar fishermen are the lack of access to information and capital. Generally, people do not have sufficient personal savings, while the absence of assets causes limitations in obtaining banking fund facilitation for additional capital and business development (Munandar & Darmawan, 2020).

Another factor that also affects the poverty structure in the village is the consumptive nature of the community due to the assumption that marine resource will not run out. However, if the sea catch has been reduced, they will start to migrating again. This cycle of pragmatic culture also encourages many people in the village of Lontar to choose to work abroad as IMW rather than try to find opportunities to work in the country or take advantage of the potential of the resources around them.

In practice, the recruitment and placement process for IMW is usually carried out by various methods, both legal and illegal. BP2MI noted that during January to October 2021 alone, there were thousands of reports and complaints received, including IMW asking to be sent home for job opportunity fraud (BP2MI.go.id). IMW problems are complex enough to involve family relationships (Sena, 2018). Although there is no specific data in the Lontar Village case, existing research proves that PMI families are very vulnerable to the risk of divorce (Karlina, Arif & Sodikin, 2017). Miladiyanto (2016) found that the reasons for divorce in IMW families generally include: (1) economic level has not improved; (2) passive communication; (3) differences; (4) unfaithfulness/infidelity; (5) inner livelihood problems; (6) mutual suspicion.

4.2 Establishment of Kawan PMI in Lontar Village

In general, the policy for the establishment of the Indonesian Migrant Workers' Volunteer Community (Kawan PMI) is based on the Regulation of the Head of the National Agency for the Placement and Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers Number 6 of 2017 concerning the Family Community of Migrant Workers which was later amended by the Regulation of the

Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2022. The birth of the regulation is motivated by the high public interest in working abroad, but it is not comparable to the public's knowledge on how to migrate procedurally and safe.

Gatot Hermawan, the Director of Empowerment of the National Agency for the Placement and Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers (BNP2TKI) at that time, initiated the idea of forming Kawan PMI in Lontar Village. Currently BNP2TKI has been revitalized to become the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). This is as stated by Mr. Jongga as the representative of BP2MI Serang:

“The basis for its formation is actually from the central program according to the regulations of the head of the agency. Why the lontar village? because it is identical to PMI, even to the point that being called the "dollar village".”

The village government and local residents initially rejected the empowerment activities because they did not yet understand the benefits of these activities. The village side accepted and enthusiastically supported the BP2MI program after receiving adequate explanation and understanding.

According to Mr. Sudrajat, the Community Organizer (CO) of Kawan PMI Lontar Village, there are three reasons for the formation of Kawan PMI in Lontar Village: first, there is information that many parties benefit from the large number of sending and placing IMW from Lontar Village, but the fact is that many people who work as IMW actually do not feel a better life even though they have worked abroad; second, there are many problems faced by people who work as IMW; and third, the formation of Kawan PMI is based on the intention and passion to provide empowerment and knowledge to IMW.

According to the BP2MI Serang, Kawan PMI was founded in the village of Lontar to combat syndicates and brokers, particularly by providing information on how to work legally, as well as advocacy and empowerment training. This is reflected in Kawan PMI's organizational structure, which has three Community Organizers (CO) in three fields, namely job information or jobs info, case assistance, and empowerment.

4.3 The Empowerment by Kawan PMI in Community Empowerment Aspect

4.3.1 Enabling Aspect

In general, there are three aspects to the concept of community empowerment, namely the enabling aspect (potential development), empowering (potential strengthening), and protecting (protection) (Mulyawan, 2016). The first aspect, namely "enabling", is intended as an effort to create an atmosphere or climate that allows the potential of the community to develop (Kartasasmita, 1996).

The presence of Kawan PMI in Lontar Village is not only intended to reduce the placement of non-procedural IMW in Lontar Village but, more than that, to develop the potential of the village community so that they do not always depend on income from working as IMW. Kawan PMI by involving BP2MI Serang, then initiated the formation of the PMI Purna community

based on business groups. As stated by Mr. Jongga, as the Advisor for Kawan PMI from BP2MI Serang:

"Our policy is indeed to create a business group. At least there is an effort to encourage and change the mindset of villagers who work abroad to be able to do their own business. So we are not talking about the number of people we can train, but how big the business group that we have created can grow and be independent. "

Tanjung (2016) argues that the real manifestation of enabling efforts can be done through the declaration of empowerment programs by involving the community in each of these empowerment programs. The orientation of empowerment itself is the growth of independence (Malik & Mulyono, 2017).

Among several empowerment activities that have been given are entrepreneurship training for the formation of cooperatives and SMEs (2018), expanding product marketing through market places (2019), batik training (2017), training in making beaded crafts (2021), training on processed grass cultivation (2018), and so on.

4.3.2. Empowering Aspect

The second aspect of empowerment is empowering, which is an effort to strengthen the potential of the community through concrete steps by providing various inputs and opening a number of opportunities that will make the community more empowered (Suryani, 2019). The empowering process is intended as a follow-up to the enabling process or creating an atmosphere. This follow-up is carried out by providing various inputs and opening access to various opportunities that will make the community more empowered (Mardikanto and Soebiato, 2013).

Kawan PMI made a number of efforts to strengthen the potential of IMW and Retired IMW in addition to attempting to create a productive environment for them. This is accomplished through a series of collaborations and training activities focused on the potential of the Lontar Village community, the majority of whom work as fishermen and seaweed farmers in addition to being migrant workers.

Usually the fishermen will immediately sell the catch without any further processing which results in a low selling price. The same problem also occurs in relation to seaweed farmers, where the main obstacles faced are related to product promotion and marketing due to lack of knowledge and access to information. This is as stated by Mr. Jongga:

"They have suffered a loss in product competitiveness." They are under-marketed." As a result, it is difficult to develop into something larger than a home industry when it merely grows. For example, seaweed lunkhead products

This phenomenon was caught by the village government and the PMI comrades of Lontar Village, which were then managed in collaboration with the Technical Service Unit (UPT) of BP2MI Serang district. PMI Friends Together with UPT BP2MI did a number of problem mappings and selected a number of priority programs. Some of these empowerment programs

include training on milkfish cultivation (2019), training on seaweed cultivation technology (2017), training on processed seaweed (2018), processed seaweed noodles (2018), and training on cultivation of green shellfish and processed seafood (2019).

Empowerment in the form of business incubation like this at least has a number of benefits for the community, including opening up new business opportunities and people getting entrepreneurial skills that will ultimately improve their standard of living and welfare (Asmirelda, et al., 2020). As emphasized by Mr. Andi, the Head of Lontar Village:

"The point is how the central and regional governments encourage people to have their own income in their own environment, in their own villages." Through various training, it is now very helpful to increase IMW's family's economic income. Now, this is what the village government, together with Kawan PMI, is pushing.

Based on the information from Mr. Jongga from UPT BP2MI Serang and Mr. Sudrajat as Community Organizer (CO) of Kawan PMI, a number of training programs were carried out aimed at strengthening the potential that already existed in Lontar Village. Both in terms of identifying new products, improving the quality of existing products by providing some knowledge to the public.

As explained by Suryani (2019), the most basic efforts in this empowerment include increasing knowledge, health status, or access to sources of economic progress such as capital, technology, information, employment opportunities, or markets that can be reached by the lowest-income communities, whose power is very minimal. In addition to socialization and training, empowerment by Kawan PMI is also carried out by providing information related to available jobs to the Lontar Village community (jobs info). This is done by the Kawan PMI community organizer in the job information division. However, the information provided is not only limited to job opportunities abroad but also includes job opportunities that are open in the country, especially around the Serang sub-district. This is done so that people do not always depend on being IMW, so they have to leave their relatives.

4.3.3. Protecting Aspect

The third aspect of empowerment emphasizes that empowering also means protecting (Kartasmita, 1996: 159-160). In this case, Friedmann (1994) asserts that community empowerment is not only limited to the economic field but also politically, so that in the end, the community will have a bargaining position both nationally and internationally.

Based on information from BP2MI Serang, problems that often occur at Lontar Village IMWs are non-procedural migration or illegal placements. This is because the Middle East is still a tremendous attraction for the people of Lontar Village. A number of ways were also carried out to lure the people of Lontar Village to want to work as migrant workers, among others, by luring a certain amount of money from the sponsor to those who are having economic difficulty. Even by preparing such "economic traps" in the form of debt loans. When people are no longer able to pay their debts, that's where the sponsors offer the opportunity to work as laborers abroad.

Together with the village government, Lontar Village PMI Comrades are trying to prevent the illegal departure and placement of PMI. In the context of protecting PMIs, PMI Friends have two main functions: first, to equip the prospective PMI community to work through safe procedural channels and avoid exploitation; second, to provide assistance to PMIs who have problems. In the context of Lontar Village, this effort was carried out preventively through briefing and outreach regarding the risks and impacts of illegally departing PMI, and by visiting PMI candidates door to door to invite discussion and build awareness among PMI candidates to cancel their intention to migrate illegally.

In addition to minimizing PMI's non-procedural departures, PMI friends also try to provide assistance and advocacy when it is found that PMI is experiencing problems. As stated by Mr. Sudrajat as CO of Kawan PMI:

“When a PMI family member reports to us about his family's problems abroad, we always respond, and always advocate, and take the case to law enforcer or BP2MI Serang.”

According to Adi (2002), empowerment does more than just solve problems; it also prepares structures and systems in society to be proactive and responsive to societal needs and problems. In this context, Kawan PMI's protection efforts are viewed as a proactive and responsive effort to prevent non-procedural migration and placements, including consulting and advocating for those experiencing difficulties abroad.

4.4 Impact of Empowerment on IMW Resilience

4.4.1 IMW Resilience in Facing Economic Risk

The presence of Kawan PMI with a series of empowerment efforts that have been carried out in principle has a positive effect on protective factors, both in terms of individual resources, as well as social resources that support the resilience of the PMI and retired PMI communities in overcoming existing economic problems. With entrepreneurship training, marketing, business incubation, and facilitation of capital loans by involving BP2MI, banking institutions and private parties, it is enough to help the PMI community in opening new business opportunities and increasing their income.

Table 4.2: Informant Interview Minutes

No	Informan	Response to Empowerment Activities	Benefits felt
1	Marina (IMW)	<i>"I'm happy, so there's progress"</i>	"Now, thank God, we have opened a small shop, a basic food shop"
2	Roshita (IMW)	"It's very helpful, because those of us who are at home are motivated not to work abroad anymore"	"The benefits are many. So you can make knick-knacks, like brooches. the important thing is having a good tools"
3	Humaerah (IMW)	"Yes, it's useful, if you get it, the knowledge can be a business"	"we already know the ways, so if that's the case, we can sell it. Yes, now I can make mask connectors, make bracelets, make necklaces, and much more"
4	Andi (IMW)	"Yes, that's great, in my opinion. Can help PMI who is here"	"we are getting more knowledge, so we don't have to depend on working abroad anymore, so fishermen can take advantage of the potential that is around them too"
5.	Desi (IMW)	"It's good, we just need to continue, because we still need a lot of training"	"we gain more knowledge, more experience, that means more income too"

Source: Primary data

Based on the results of interviews with the number of PMIs in Lontar Village who have participated in empowerment activities in Kawan PMI (table 4.2), it shows that, in general, the activities carried out have received positive responses. A number of empowerment efforts carried out by PMI Friends in Lontar Village are considered quite effective in creating an environment that motivates PMIs to become entrepreneurs.

The results of the empowerment program is quite significant. According to 2019 data, there are around 1,021 residents of Lontar Village who are working as seaweed farmers. Mr. Sudrajat also stated that many MSMEs have been developed whose products are based on processed seaweed and are marketed through cooperatives and a number of shops in Serang sub-district. Also stated by Mr. Sudrajat:

"About the empowerment, thank God, many villagers are entrepreneurs now and have their own MSMEs. One of them is a cooperative that accommodates products from PMI that have received empowerment, thereby increasing their entrepreneurship, including those whose marketing is already using the market place."

A number of training activities initiated by Kawan PMI have being a protective factor for IMW's resilience in dealing with economic problems. In terms of individual resources, the empowerment by Kawan PMI has changed the mindset of the IMW community from a consumptive culture to an entrepreneurial one. Kawan PMI is also become a social resource for the business groups and product marketing assistance.

4.4.2 IMW Resilience in Facing Domestic Risks

In fact, the issues confronting IMW are frequently quite complex, even involving family relationships (Sena, 2018). A family member's departure to become a migrant worker fundamentally alters the structure and order of the family. This has implications for changing roles in the family, such as female migrant worker (Muchimah, 2020).

In this context, the community organizer of Kawan PMI, Mr. Sudrajat, admitted that the presence of Kawan PMI acted as a mediator when problems occurred in the IMW's family environment. According to him, domestic issues do sometimes occur in IMW families, but their intensity has decreased since the presence of Kawan PMI in Lontar Village. In detail, he stated:

“Yes, there used to be, Ma'am. We admit that there are some privacy issues among IMW family. But thank God now it's not as much as before. Because we always provide an understanding about migration. We can also help as much as we can to resolute the conflict if needed.”

Based on this, the presence of Kawan PMI as a protective factor does not have a significant impact on the ability of IMW's families to deal with internal household problems. At least two reasons: first, domestic problems are usually sensitive and private matters, so not many people are willing to open up and involve outsiders to solve them. Nevertheless, there has been a collective effort from the PMI Friends and the PMI Association to provide moral support to its members who have household problems. This is important because, psychologically, individuals who face domestic problems need support from those closest to them. (Muthmainnah, 2021).

4.4.3 IMW Resilience in Facing the Risks of Migration

Based on data obtained from the Lontar Village government, there have been many cases and problems that befell IMW from Lontar Village abroad that were able to be resolved thanks to the assistance of the Kawan PMI. Throughout 2018 to 2019, no less than 43 cases of complaints were successfully facilitated by Kawan PMI. Thus, it also plays an important role as protective factors that can increase IMW's resilience in facing the risks of their job.

The contribution of the empowerment by Kawan PMI in Lontar Village was also explained by Mr. Sudrajat who stated:

"Thank God, now those who migrate illegally and get into trouble abroad are far less. Because we from the Kawan PMI routinely carry out socialization to the mass community of IMW and candidates. We also go door to door and use social media to promote safety and procedural migration."

Tabel 4.3: Risalah Wawancara Informan

No	Informan	Problems faced at work	How to overcome
1	Marina (IMW)	"There are no serious problems, ma'am, at least it's just a language barrier "	"I Just learn slowly, in time you will be able to do it little by little "
2	Roshita (IMW)	"Yes, the language, as well as the food it seems. I rarely communicate with the employer "	"Just get used to it, listen to it often, later it will be by itself "
3	Andi (IMW)	"Thank God there wasn't any, because before leaving, I also attended briefings from Kawan PMI and BP2MI Serang. "	"The important thing is that we often coordinate, with the family, if necessary to the Kawan PMI or BP2MI "
5.	Desi (IMW)	"The problem is maybe the habits are new, the working hours outside are different"	"Yes, I have to be diligent, adapt smartly, we work with people abroad, so we have to be patient too"
6	Humaerah (IMW)	"actually the work is the same, it's just that sometimes the household appliances are a bit different, so you have to adjust"	"I just have to learn a lot, especially before I go to work again, you have to take a lot of training and debriefing, one of which is from Kawan PMI."

Source: Primary Data (edited)

Based on interviews with a number of informants who are PMIs who recently returned from abroad (Asia and the Middle East), no significant problems were found. This is because all of the informants were PMIs who went through procedural lines and had received briefings from PMI and BP2MI Serang friends. Basically, the PMI Friends in Lontar Village have played a role as a forum for PMI's access to the protection and information they really need when they leave and while they are abroad. This makes PMI colleagues one of the protective factors that strongly supports the ability of PMI Lontar Village to survive in the face of various risks that may arise in their profession as migrant workers.

5. CONCLUSION

From the analysis of community empowerment in Kawan PMI in Lontar Village, it can be concluded that the empowerment efforts are aimed at preventing non-procedural placements of migrant workers, in addition to increasing their capacity and economy. Conceptual community empowerment efforts have fulfilled the aspects of community empowerment, which include aspects of enabling, empowering, and protecting.

The enabling aspect is carried out by creating an environment that supports the potential of the community through the formation of the PMI Purna association based on business groups. Empowering aspects are realized by strengthening community potential, such as business incubation-based entrepreneurship training and providing job information. The protecting aspect is carried out in the form of socialization on the dangers of non-procedural departures, as well as providing advocacy services for problematic IMWs.

Analysis of the impact of empowerment on IMW resilience was carried out by looking at the effect of empowerment on protective factors (individual and social resources) in dealing with economic, domestic, and migration risks. Regarding economic risks, empowerment by Kawan PMI in Lontar Village has changed the mindset of individuals in the IMW community, who were initially pragmatic and consumeristic, to become entrepreneurs. Kawan PMI also supports social resources by becoming an education center in increasing community capacity as well as a facilitator for a number of aids and partnerships. Regarding domestic risks, Kawan PMI provides moral support for the resilience of individuals who have domestic issues, while from a social perspective, it acts as a mediator as well as a forum for consultation for members. In the context of resilience to the migration risks, the majority of PMI IMW in Lontar Village were able to survive due to high motivation after participating in empowerment activities. In terms of social resources, Kawan PMI also acts as a forum for IMW's access to advocacy services.

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